

BIM-based design validation for Fire Stations

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Abstract

Design quality relies on ensuring effective solutions for the building and its compliance with regulation codes. In the context of Fire Emergency Services facilities, the building design can have a direct impact on the efficacy of emergency response operations. Factors such as the turnout time, which means the time between the emergency call being received to the dispatching of the first unit, can be significantly affected by decisions made during the design process. Moreover, elements like travel distances within corridors and spatial clearance profoundly influence operational efficiency. The industry's current manual workflows for this phase often lead to inefficiencies and rework, and there is limited research available that integrates automatic rule-checking and design of these facilities.

This research utilizes the Design Science Research methodology to develop and evaluate a set of tools that automatically validate design requirements in BIM models of fire stations. First, the rules were identified and interpreted using RASE methodology and pseudo-codes. Second, the algorithms were translated into Revit Dynamo using Visual Programming Language. In sequence, the evaluation of the artifact included real-world fire station designs, as this study was conducted in collaboration with an architectural firm with years of experience in

designing Emergency Response facilities. Finally, the artifact was tested by a designated employee from the firm, to ensure it met their intended objectives.

The findings of this study are expected to contribute to improve the design quality and compliance in emergency facilities and bring a new initiative of integrating BIM into the architectural design process. In a broader aspect, this work aims to foster safer environments for firefighters and the communities they serve by improving design validation processes and ensuring that critical factors influencing emergency response operations are addressed. The insights gained from this research are expected to have a lasting impact in the specialized field of fire station design, promoting innovation and efficiency in architectural practice.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/SQBnQ3h0eYE>

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